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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF SIMVASTATIN FLOATING TABLETS FOR CONTROLLED RELEASE

N. G. Raghavendra Rao^{1*}, M. Laharika²

¹GRD [PG] Institute of Management and Technology, Rajpur, Dehradun – 248009, Uttarakhand, India.

²Graviti Pharmaceutical Private Limited, IDA Pashamylaram, Hyderabad - 502307, Telangana, India.

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ABSTRACT

Simvastatin is a lipid-lowering agent that is derived synthetically from a fermentation product of *Aspergillus terreus*. Simvastatin is a Hypolipidemic used to control elevated cholesterol or hypercholesterolemia. The primary uses of Simvastatin are for the treatment of dyslipidemia and the prevention of cardiovascular disease. Floating tablets of Simvastatin were developed by direct compression method to increase the gastric retention time using HPMC K4M, Carbopol and sodium CMC polymers used and the mixture of the sodium bicarbonate, citric acid anhydrous as gas generating agents. The results of Pre-compressional and post-compression parameters were within IP prescribed limits. All the formulations (FB1-FB10) prepared the formulations FB1, FB2 and FB8 fails to float. Among all the formulations batch FB7 was the best formulation which showed buoyancy lag time 2 min and the tablet remained buoyant for 12hrs. The floating capacity increased in these formulations and floated with less lag time due to the high concentration of gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate. DSC and FTIR studies revealed that there was no incompatibility of the drug with the excipients used. The stability study conducted as per the ICH guidelines and the formulations were found to be stable. From this study, it can be concluded that the FB7 was the best formulation retained for longer periods of time in the stomach and provides controlled release of the drug and may improve bioavailability.

Corresponding author

Dr. N.G. Raghavendra Rao

Director and Professor

Dept of Pharmacy,

GRD [PG] Institute of Management and Technology,

Rajpur Road, Dehradun - 248009, Uttarakhand, India.

+91 9966794479 & +91 9448570193

nraghu@rediffmail.com & drnraghu@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Oral delivery of drugs is by far the most preferable route of drug delivery due to the ease of administration, patient compliance, non-evasive in nature and flexibility formulation. From immediate release to site specific delivery, oral dosage forms have really progressed. A gastric drug delivery system (GFDDS) can overcome at least some of these problems and is particularly useful for drugs that are primarily absorbed in the duodenum and upper jejunum segments. The GFDDS is able to prolong the retention time of a dosage form in the stomach, thereby improving the oral bioavailability of the drug [1-2].

Poor bioavailability has been recorded for some drugs formulated in sustained-release dosage forms. Their narrow absorption window, lower solubility at high pH values, or enzymatic degradation in the intestinal or colonic environments was the reason of decreased bioavailability [3-7]. For this, it has been a challenge to develop the oral controlled-release dosage form because it is difficult to keep drugs at the targeted area inside the gastrointestinal tract [8]. Gastro retentive drug delivery systems provide dosage forms with longer residence time in the stomach and sustained-release behavior, which can improve bioavailability as well as acting locally on the stomach [9-10]. Increasing gastric residence time can be achieved either by floating systems that cause buoyancy above gastric fluid [11], high-density systems that sink to the bottom of the stomach [12], bioadhesive systems that adhere to mucosal surfaces [13], or by expandable systems that have limited emptying through the stomach pylorus due to swelling or unfolding to a larger size [14].

The floating drug delivery systems were described in the literature as early as 1968 [15]. These systems are designed to have a bulk density lower than the gastric fluid so they can remain buoyant for prolonged periods of time without affecting the gastric emptying rate [5, 16, 17]. Floating drug delivery systems can be classified as non-effervescent systems or effervescent systems [18]. Non-effervescent floating drug delivery systems swell in gastric fluid and maintain a relative stability of shape and bulk density less than the density of the gastric fluid, which assists the floating process of these dosage forms [19]. However, effervescent floating drug delivery systems based on effervescent components will liberate carbon dioxide due to the acidity of the gastric fluid. Liberated gas bubbles will be entrapped in the gel layer formed by hydrocolloids that produce an upward motion of the dosage form and maintain its buoyancy [20].

Simvastatin is a lipid-lowering agent that is derived synthetically from a fermentation product of *Aspergillus terreus*. After oral ingestion, Simvastatin, which is an inactive lactone, is hydrolyzed to the corresponding β -hydroxyacid form. This is an inhibitor of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase. This enzyme catalyzes the conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate, which is an early and rate-limiting step in the biosynthesis of cholesterol. Also, it has been reported [21, 22] that Simvastatin is more efficiently extracted by the liver than its corresponding hydroxy acid with subsequent minimization of systemic burden [23]. This suggests that compared to a conventional dosage form, a sustained/controlled release dosage form of Simvastatin might provide similar or better efficacy [24]. Simvastatin is a Hypolipidemic used to control elevated cholesterol, or hypercholesterolemia. It is a member of the Statin class of pharmaceuticals. The primary uses of Simvastatin are for the treatment of dyslipidemia and the prevention of cardiovascular disease. The $t_{1/2}$ for Simvastatin is 2 to 4 hrs and bioavailability is 5% and efficiency of protein binding is 95%. This research study provided useful information on preformulation and formulation optimization of the selected anti retroviral drugs as floating modules during development of controlled drug delivery systems containing various rate controlling polymers, to get the desired controlled release over a period of 12 hrs. The main objective of the present research work is formulation and development of floating drug delivery system containing Simvastatin, which releases the drug at controlled rate for a long period of time in the stomach [25-26].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Simvastatin drug is procured as a gift sample from Lupin labs, Private Ltd. Pune, India. HPMC K4M procured as a gift sample from AstraZeneca Pvt Ltd Bangalore. Carbopol 934, magnesium stearate and citric acid are purchased from Hi media laboratories Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. India, Sodium bicarbonate, Ethyl cellulose, Sodium CMC, MCC, lactose and talc were purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals. Mumbai. All other materials used were of pharmaceutical grade.

Drug-excipients compatibility studies:

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):

FTIR studies were carried out pure drug Simvastatin and best formulations like, FB7 and FB9. Infrared spectroscopy was performed using a Shimadzu FTIR 8300 Spectrophotometer and the spectrum was recorded in the region of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . The procedure consisted of dispersing a sample (drug and excipients, 1:1 ratio in potassium bromide (KBr) (200-400 mg) and compressing into discs by applying a pressure of 5 tons for 5 min in a hydraulic press. The pellet was placed in the light path and the spectrum was obtained.

Differential Scanning Colorimetry:

DSC studies were carried out pure drug Simvastatin and formulations like, FB7 and FB9. DSC scan of about 5mg, accurately weighed Simvastatin and other formulations were performed by using an automatic thermal analyzer system. (DSC60 Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) Sealed and perforated aluminium pans were used in the experiments for all the samples. Temperature calibrations were performed using indium as standard. An empty pan sealed in the same way as for the sample was used as a reference. The entire samples were run at a scanning rate of 10°C/min from 50-300°C.

Preparation of Simvastatin floating tablets [27-29]:

All the formulations FB1 to FB10 were prepared by direct compression method. The composition of the tablets is given in Table 1. All the formulation tablets containing drug and other excipients, were prepared by weighing drug, diluents along with natural gums and passing them through sieve no 44 to break the lumps and also for proper blending of powder, to this powder blend 0.5 % of magnesium stearate and 1 % of talc were added to each and further mixed. The resultant blends were punched to 300 mg using convex-faced punches using a multi-station rotary compression machine (Rimek mini press-II MT).

Table 1: Formulation composition Simvastatin Floating Tablets.

INGREDIENTS	FB1	FB2	FB3	FB4	FB5	FB6	FB7	FB8	FB9	FB10
Drug	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
HPMC K4M	10	20	30	40	50	50	-	-	-	-
Ethyl Cellulose	-	10	20	30	40	40	40	40	40	40
Sodium Bi Carbonate	30	30	40	40	40	50	50	40	50	40
Citric Acid	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Carbopol	-	30	30	30	30	30	100	75	125	150
Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Sodium CMC	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
MCC	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Lactose	200	150	120	100	80	70	50	85	25	10
Total	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

Evaluation of Simvastatin floating tablets:

The resultant blends were evaluated for pre-compressional parameters to find out the flow properties of powder blend. The pre-compressional parameters such as Bulk density, Tapped density, Angle of repose, Compressibility index and Hausner ratio.

Post-compressional parameter [30-35]:**Tablet weight variation:**

Twenty tablets were randomly selected and weighed. Average weight of all 20 tablets was calculated. Not more than two tablets should deviate from average weight by 7.5 % and none deviates than twice the percentage for tablets (200 mg).

Tablet thickness:

Control of physical dimension of the tablets such as sizes and thickness is essential for consumer acceptance and to maintain tablet to tablet uniformity. Thickness was measured using Vernier Calipers on 3 randomly selected samples.

Hardness:

The hardness of tablet was carried out by using Pfizer type hardness tester. The hardness of the tablet kg / cm² was measured. Tablet hardness tester was used to determine hardness of 10 randomly selected tablets.

Drug content uniformity:

Ten tablets were crushed individually in a motor and pestle. The powder was taken in 100 ml of 0.1N HCl with 1% SLS and mixed well. The solution was filtered. The drug content was determined. Not more than one tablet should be outside the limits of 85 – 115% of average content and none of them outside 75-125% of average content.

Tablet friability:

Tablets were randomly selected weighing equal to or more than 6.5g and placed in the drum of tablet friability test apparatus (Electrolab EF-1W friabilator USP). The drum was adjusted to rotate at 25 rpm for 4 min. The tablets were removed, de-dusted and accurately weighed. The percent weight loss was calculated. The loss of weight should not be more than 1% as per IP-2007. Percentage friability of tablets less than 1% was considered acceptable.

It was calculated by using following formula

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{(\text{Initial wt. of tablets} - \text{Final wt. of tablets})}{\text{Initial wt. of tablets}} \times 100$$

Disintegration Time:

The disintegration time was determined at 37±0.50⁰ C using disintegration test apparatus (Electro lab, Mumbai) in 0.1N HCL with 1% SLS..

Buoyancy lag time and total floating time [TFT]:

The buoyancy of the tablets was determined, in triplicate, according to the floating lag time method. A tablet was placed in a glass beaker, containing 100 ml of 0.1N HCl with 1% SLS kept for stirring maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The floating lag time (the time required for tablet to float from the time of tablet introduction) and total floating duration (the time during which tablet remains buoyant in the medium) were observed visually and values were noted. The duration of time by which dosage form remain buoyant is called total floating time.

Swelling studies:

The swelling behaviour of the tablets was determined. A tablet was weighed (W_1) and placed in a glass beaker with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl with 1% SLS kept for stirring maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. At time intervals, 0 to 8 hrs at every 1hr the tablet was removed and the excess surface liquid was carefully removed by a filter paper. The tablet was then reweighed (W_2). The swelling index (SI) was calculated by using the following formula.

$$\text{Swelling index} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

In vitro drug release studies (dissolution studies):

Apparatus	:	Dissolution test apparatus (USP XXIII)
Method	:	USP type 2 apparatus (paddle)
Dissolution medium	:	0.1N HCl with 1% SLS
Volume of DM	:	900 ml
Temperature	:	$37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$
Speed	:	50 rpm

Stability studies:

Stability studies were performed on optimized formulations, prepared tablets were wrapped with aluminium foil and kept in a vial. These samples were placed in a stability chamber (Thermolab, humidity and photo stability chamber) at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH another temperature $40 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH according to ICH guidelines. At regular time intervals of 15, 30, 60 and 90 days tablets were analysed for drug release lag time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:**Identification of Simvastatin:****FTIR Studies:**

The FT-IR spectra of pure drug peaks are observed in the Simvastatin pure sample and formulations FB7 and FB9 were showed same characteristic absorption bands at or near that of Simvastatin absorption bands values indicating that there was no chemical and physical change in the functional groups present in Simvastatin. [Shown in Fig 1].

Fig 1: IR spectra of pure drug Simvastatin and optimized formulations FB7 and FB8.

DSC Studies:

The study also reveals that the thermogram of pure drug Simvastatin and other formulations FB7 and FB9 [Shown in Fig 2] shows negligible changes in the melting point range. Thus the DSC thermograms study reveals that there is no any kind of interaction of the drug with different types of polymer and their excipients used during the study.

Fig 2: DSC Thermograms of pure drug Simvastatin and optimized formulations FB8 and FB9.

The Pre-compression parameters were the primary requirements to determine whether the specific material was suitable for the targeted formulation or not. The aim was to formulate the tablet formulation with direct compression method, so it was mandatory to know the bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose as those were the official requirement while choosing any material for its dosage form formulation. The results evaluated pre-compression parameters for various tablet formulations. The results were clearly indicates its suitability to be the material of choice for formulation. The values were within prescribed limits and indicated good free flowing property. The results of pre-compression parameters were given in Table 2.

Table 2: Pre-Compressional Parameters of Simvastatin floating tablets (FB1-FB10).

FC	Angle of repose ⁽⁰⁾ *	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)*	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)*	Carr's Index (%)*	Hausner ratio (Hr)*
FB1	28.13 ± 0.12	0.486 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.06	18.12 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.03
FB2	25.45 ± 0.14	0.468 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.05	19.43 ± 0.01	1.14 ± 0.02
FB3	28.67 ± 0.15	0.431 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.04	22.10 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.04
FB4	29.89 ± 0.13	0.463 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.01	24.67 ± 0.05	1.11 ± 0.06
FB5	24.34 ± 0.15	0.521 ± 0.01	0.63 ± 0.03	17.32 ± 0.04	1.14 ± 0.02
FB6	23.13 ± 0.11	0.541 ± 0.07	0.64 ± 0.02	18.45 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.03
FB7	28.15 ± 0.14	0.561 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.03	21.78 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.01
FB8	29.67 ± 0.15	0.421 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.02	28.26 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.03
FB9	23.90 ± 0.16	0.458 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.04	26.90 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.05
FB10	23.23 ± 0.12	0.437 ± 0.05	0.62 ± 0.02	28.78 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.02

FC=Formulation code *All the values expressed as mean ± SD, n=3

All the formulations were evaluated for various parameters (Results were shown in Table 3) like hardness of the tablets were measured, the hardness of tablets of each batch ranged between 5-7 kg/cm². This ensures good handling characteristics of all tablets. The mean thickness was (n=3) almost uniform in all the formulations, the values ranged from 4.06 ± 0.105 to 4.35 ± 0.121 mm. The standard deviation values indicated that the all the formulations were within the range. The values of friability test were tabulated in Table 3. The % friability was found in all designed formulations in the range of 0.43 ± 0.03 to 0.87 ± 0.08 to be well within the approved range (less than 1%) and all the formulations ensures that the tablets were mechanically stable. The percentage of drug content was found to be between 71.12 to 100.90 of Simvastatin, which was within acceptable limits. Table 3 showed the results of drug content uniformity in each batch. All the formulations were evaluated for various parameters, like Hardness, thickness, friability and percentage of drug contents of all tablets from batch FB1 to FB10. In all the formulations, all the post-compressional parameters results revealed that the tablets were within the range of pharmacopoeial limit. Results of water uptake study showed that the order of swelling in these polymers could indicate the rates at which the preparations are able to absorb water and swell. Maximum liquid uptake and swelling of polymer was achieved up to 7 hrs and then gradually decreased due to erosion. The swelling of polymers used in these tablets (HPMC K4M, carbopol and sodium CMC) could be determined by water uptake of the tablets. The complete swelling was achieved by the end of 7 hrs. The swelling index was in range of 113.55 ± 0.62 to 198.01 ± 0.68.

Table 3: Post-Compressional Parameters Simvastatin floating tablets (FB1-FB10).

FC	Thickness (mm)*	Hardness (kg/cm ²)*	Friability (%)*	Drug content (%)*	Weight variation (mg)**	Swelling index (%)**
FB1	4.06 ± 0.105	5.4 ± 0.1	0.48 ± 0.09	71.12	301.10 ± 1.02	113.55 ± 0.62
FB2	4.12 ± 0.125	5.8 ± 0.2	0.56 ± 0.07	90.06	304.11 ± 1.21	135.80 ± 0.45
FB3	4.25 ± 0.145	6.0 ± 0.1	0.61 ± 0.10	80.12	298.01 ± 0.12	152.36 ± 0.24
FB4	4.20 ± 0.012	5.8 ± 0.3	0.43 ± 0.03	83.97	302.03 ± 1.13	115.44 ± 0.36
FB5	4.36 ± 0.032	5.9 ± 0.5	0.45 ± 0.06	100.9	301.12 ± 1.19	123.74 ± 0.57
FB6	4.16 ± 0.113	5.7 ± 0.2	0.67 ± 0.12	84.3	299.21 ± 1.23	136.11 ± 0.48
FB7	4.26 ± 0.125	6.5 ± 0.1	0.45 ± 0.11	89.42	296.12 ± 1.14	167.37 ± 0.51
FB8	4.14 ± 0.099	6.0 ± 0.5	0.78 ± 0.02	72.24	305.05 ± 1.16	176.56 ± 0.71
FB9	4.35 ± 0.121	6.2 ± 0.5	0.87 ± 0.08	71.47	300.09 ± 1.17	184.24 ± 0.37
FB10	4.32 ± 0.120	6.8 ± 0.3	0.65 ± 0.04	76.28	302.03 ± 0.06	198.01 ± 0.68

FC=Formulation code, **All the values expressed as mean ±SD, n=20, *All the values expressed as mean ±SD, n=3.

Formulations from FB1, FB2, and FB8 did not float; this was due to the lower percentage of gas generating agent. The formulation FB3, FB4, FB5 and FB6 floated but the lag time was more and floating time is less. For the formulations FB7 and FB9 the duration of buoyancy was more than 12 hrs, the floating capacity increased in these formulations and floated with less lag time due to high concentration of gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate induced CO₂ generation in the pressure of dissolution medium. The gas generation is trapped & protected within the gel formed by hydration of the polymers, thus decreasing the density of tablet. In the study with 200 ml 0.1N HCL with 1% SLS without paddle it was found that the floating lag time decreased and the duration increased for the same formulations. In all the formulations buoyancy time ranges from 4 - 12 hrs and lag time ranges from 2 - 52 min. All the results were given in Table 4 and Fig 3.

Table 4: Floating ability of Simvastatin floating tablets of (FB1-FB10).

Sl. No	FC	LAG TIME (min)	FLOATING TIME (Hour)
1	FB1	Fail	-
2	FB2	Do not float	-
3	FB3	07 min	>12 hrs
4	FB4	11 min	>12 hrs
5	FB5	16 min	>4 hrs
6	FB6	09 min	>12 hrs
7	FB7	01 min 30 Sec	>12 hrs
8	FB8	Do not float	-
9	FB9	03 min 30Sec	>12 hrs
10	FB10	06 min	>12 hrs

Fig 3: Floating Lag Time Vs Formulation FB1-FB10.

In-vitro Drug Release Studies of Simvastatin Formulations:

The release rate of Simvastatin from floating tablet was determined by Dissolution Tester apparatus **DS-8050** Lab India. The dissolution test was performed using 900ml 0.1N HCL with 1% SLS at 37°C± 0.5°C. The drug release from the formulations FB1-FB10 was found to be 76.01, 94.034, 88.51, 82.32, 76.36, 99.28, 74.38, and 70.51% in 12 hrs. Among all the formulations FB7 formulation shows the drug release around 99.28% within 12 hrs. From the in-vitro drug release study it is found to be as the concentration of the polymer increases the drug release decreases. The dissolution profiles of all the formulations are shown in Fig 4-5 and Table 5. From results the formulation containing large concentration of high viscosity polymers induced formation of strong viscous gel layer that leads to decreased water diffusion into the tablet which results in decrease drug release.

Table 5: In-vitro Drug Release Studies of Simvastatin FB1-FB10 formulations.

FC	4 th Hour	8 th Hour	10 th Hour	12 th hour
FB1	92.25 ± 0.12	-	-	-
FB2	42.00 ± 0.17	76.01 ± 0.28	-	-
FB3	44.81 ± 0.55	77.56 ± 0.30	87.21 ± 0.12	94.03 ± 0.12
FB4	37.25 ± 0.19	69.51 ± 0.52	82.87 ± 0.77	88.51 ± 0.52
FB5	36.17 ± 0.28	63.67 ± 0.46	76.42 ± 0.24	82.32 ± 0.27
FB6	34.31 ± 0.35	58.14 ± 0.43	67.05 ± 0.27	76.36 ± 0.62
FB7	45.74 ± 0.56	77.61 ± 0.60	89.28 ± 0.71	99.28 ± 0.52
FB8	40.66 ± 0.33	66.09 ± 0.45	-	-
FB9	33.98 ± 0.82	56.97 ± 0.67	68.24 ± 0.76	74.38 ± 0.52
FB10	31.76 ± 0.22	54.81 ± 0.45	64.68 ± 0.58	70.51 ± 0.64

FC=Formulation code, All values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3,

Fig 4: Release profile of Simvastatin formulations FB1-FB5.

Fig 5: Release profile of Simvastatin formulations FB6-FB10.

In-vitro drug release kinetic studies:

The dissolution profiles of all the batches were fitted to zero-order, by plotting cumulative amount of drug release versus time, first-order by plotting log cumulative percentage of drug remaining versus time, Higuchi, by plotting cumulative percentage of release versus square root of time, Korsmeyer-Peppas equation models by plotting log cumulative percentage of drug released versus log time. A result shown in Table 6 reveals that all Simvastatin formulations FB1-FB10 follow zero order kinetics as correlation coefficient (r^2) values are higher than that of first order release kinetics. The calculated n values from power law equation for drug release profiles were between 0.870-0.997 with a correlation coefficient (r^2) values >0.94, suggest that drug release mechanism from Simvastatin Floating tablets followed non-Fickian (anomalous) transport mechanism.

Table 6: In-vitro Drug release kinetics of FB1-FB10 Formulations.

FC	Zero Order R ² Value	First Order R ² Value	Higuchi R ² Value	Peppas R ² Value	Peppas n value
FB1	0.999	0.941	0.954	0.884	0.224
FB2	0.984	0.952	0.939	0.968	0.749
FB3	0.972	0.957	0.973	0.995	0.715
FB4	0.984	0.951	0.953	0.982	0.741
FB5	0.984	0.980	0.962	0.994	0.782
FB6	0.987	0.988	0.967	0.995	0.762
FB7	0.982	0.792	0.977	0.998	0.724
FB8	0.989	0.992	0.975	0.996	0.708
FB9	0.989	0.993	0.974	0.996	0.692
FB10	0.985	0.996	0.970	0.998	0.712

FC=Formulation code

The Table 7 shows the parameters of the tablets after stability study. The promising formulations were subjected to short term stability study. The best formulations were selected. After three month the tablets were again analyzed for the hardness, drug content uniformity and floating time. No significant changes in other parameters were observed in the Simvastatin tablets prepared with different polymers all formulations was within the acceptable limits.

Table 7: Stability study data.

S.No.	Formulation code	Month	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Drug content	Buoyancy lag time(sec)
Result for 25 ⁰ C / 65% RH					
1	FB7	1 st	5.9	89.42	2min 28sec
		2 nd	6.1	86.37	2min 42sec
		3 rd	6.4	84.56	3 min
Result for 40 ⁰ C / 75% RH					
2	FB7	1 st	5.9	89.42	2min 39sec
		2 nd	6.2	85.78	2min 55sec
		3 rd	6.3	83.42	3 min 5 sec

FC=Formulation code

CONCLUSION

Studies have been carried out to develop Floating tablets of Simvastatin with polymers HPMC K4M, Ethyl cellulose and Sodium CMC. Ten different formulations were prepared and the formulations were tested for floating characterization like floating lag time and floating time, in-vitro dissolution studies. Based on the results of floating and dissolution studies FB7 formulation shows the drug release around 99% within 12 hrs. Among all the formulations batch FB7 was the best formulation which showed buoyancy lag time 2 min and the tablet remained buoyant for 12hrs and dissolution studies FB7 formulation shows the drug release around 99.28 % within 12 hrs has better control release of drug. Finally it can be concluded that, the formulation retained for longer periods of time in the stomach (spatial control) and provides controlled release of the drug. Hence, Simvastatin Floating tablets retained for longer periods of time in the stomach which may leads to improve the therapeutic effect of the drug by increasing its bioavailability.

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